

Transition Metal Complexes of N-Benzoyl-N'-o-Aminophenyl Thiocarbamide as Antifungal Agents

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Binuclear complexes of the type, $[M_2(BAPTC)_2X_4]$ where BAPTC=N-Benzoyl-N'-o-aminophenyl thiocarbamide, $M=Cu(II)$, $Ni(II)$ or $Co(II)$, $X=Cl^-$, Br^- , NO_2^- or ClO_4^- have been prepared from neutral medium and characterized on the basis of elemental analyses, magnetic and spectral studies. Infrared spectra manifest the co-ordination of the ligand to the metal ion through the amine nitrogen, thiocarbonyl sulphur and carbonyl oxygen atoms. Complexes of $Cu(II)$ and $Co(II)$ have octahedral geometry whereas $Ni(II)$ complexes have tetragonal structure as indicated from electronic spectra. All the complexes possess low magnetic moments and their covalent nature has been ascertained from conductometric study in methyl cyanide. Fungicidal screening of the complexes by agar plate technique shows them to be antifungal against *Aspergillus niger*, *Fusarium oxysporium* and *Helminthosporium oryzae*.

METAL complexes of sulphur donor ligands have received great attention during recent years¹ because of their versatile use as antifungal and antibacterial agents. A survey of literature reveals that compounds containing both C=O and C=S groups possess significant fungicidal activity². Despite the fact that a variety of sulphur donor ligands have been studied^{3,4} for the synthesis of metal complexes it appears that N-benzoyl-N'-o-aminophenyl thiocarbamide (BAPTC) having both C=O and C=S groups has not been used. The ligand BAPTC has multi-coordination sites: one thiocarbonyl S, two thioamide N, one carbonyl O and one exocyclic NH_2 group. In view of biological importance of sulphur donor ligands we attempted to prepare a few metal complexes with BAPTC and to evaluate their antifungal activities against *Aspergillus niger*, *Fusarium oxysporium* and *Helminthosporium oryzae*.

Experimental

Materials: N-Benzoyl-N'-o-aminophenyl thiocarbamide (BAPTC) was prepared following the procedure reported by Horning^{5,2}. Analysis: Calculated for $C_{14}H_{13}CONHCSNHC_6H_4NH_2$ (BAPTC): S, 11.81; N, 15.50%, Found: S, 11.79; N, 15.46%.

Bis(N-Benzoyl-N'-o-aminophenyl thiocarbamide) tetrachloro dicopper(II), $[Cu_2(BAPTC)_2Cl_4]$: An alcoholic solution of $CuCl_2 \cdot 2H_2O$ (0.005 mole) was treated with a solution of the ligand (1.35 g, 0.005 mole) in acetone. The resulting mixture was stirred vigorously when a greenish-yellow complex precipitated. It was filtered, washed with alcohol followed by acetone and analysed after drying *in vacuo*. Analysis: Calculated for $Cu_2(C_{14}H_{13}N_3OS)_2Cl_4$: S, 7.89; N, 10.36; Cl, 17.51; Cu, 15.66%, Found: S, 7.91; N, 10.49; Cl, 17.43; Cu, 15.48%.

Bis(N-Benzoyl-N'-o-aminophenyl thiocarbamide) tetrabromo dicopper(II), $[Cu_2(BAPTC)_2Br_4]$: An acetone solution of the ligand (2.72 g, 0.01 mole) was added dropwise to a stirred solution of cupric bromide (2.6 g, 0.01 mole) in ethanol when the colour of the solution gradually changed to pale green. The resulting solution was warmed for a few minutes and cooled overnight. Pale green crystals separated out which was filtered, washed with ethanol and analysed after drying in vacuum for 12 hrs. Analysis: Calculated for $Cu_2(C_{14}H_{13}N_3OS)_2Br_4$: S, 6.49; N, 8.53; Br, 32.09; Cu, 12.89%, Found: S, 6.52; N, 8.61; Br, 31.83; Cu, 12.85%.

Bis(N-Benzoyl-N'-o-aminophenyl thiocarbamide) tetranitrato dicopper(II), $[Cu_2(BAPTC)_2(NO_3)_4]$: N-Benzoyl-N'-o-aminophenyl thiocarbamide (2.72 g, 0.01 mole) and copper(II) nitrate tetrahydrate (2.4 g, 0.01 mole) were dissolved separately in 20 ml of acetone and the whole mixture was refluxed on a water bath for several hrs. The colour of the solution gradually deepened to blood red. On cooling red crystals were obtained which were collected by filtration, dried and analysed. Analysis: Calculated for $Cu_2(C_{14}H_{13}N_3OS)_2(NO_3)_4$: S, 6.97; N, 15.27; Cu, 13.84%, Found: S, 6.88; N, 15.42; Cu, 13.63%.

Bis(N-Benzoyl-N'-o-aminophenyl thiocarbamide) tetraperchlorato dicopper(II), $[Cu_2(BAPTC)_2(ClO_4)_4]$: A solution of copper(II) perchlorate was heated on a water bath with the solution of the ligand in the molar ratio 1:1 for about 3 hrs using acetone as the refluxing medium. On slow evaporation of the mixture, a blue coloured substance separated which was filtered and analysed after being dried in vacuum for about 24 hrs. Analysis: Calculated for $Cu_2(C_{14}H_{13}N_3OS)_2(ClO_4)_4$: S, 5.99; N, 7.87; Cu, 11.91%, Found: S, 5.82; N, 7.96; Cu, 11.88%.

Bis(N-Benzoyl-N'-o-aminophenyl thiocarbamide) tetrachloro dicobalt(II), $[\text{Co}_2(\text{BAPTC})_2\text{Cl}_4]$: This was prepared as greenish blue crystals in a manner analogous to $[\text{Cu}_2(\text{BAPTC})_2(\text{ClO}_4)_4]$. Analysis: Calculated for $\text{Co}_2(\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{13}\text{N}_3\text{OS})_2\text{Cl}_4$: S, 7.98; N, 10.48; Cl, 17.71; Co, 14.70%. Found: S, 7.86; N, 10.54; Cl, 17.73; Co, 14.62%.

Bis(N-Benzoyl-N'-o-aminophenyl thiocarbamide) tetrabromo dicobalt(II), $[\text{Co}_2(\text{BAPTC})_2\text{Br}_4]$: This was prepared as dove grey crystals by a method similar to the corresponding copper(II) complex. Analysis: Calculated for $\text{Co}_2(\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{13}\text{N}_3\text{OS})_2\text{Br}_4$: S, 6.56; N, 8.66; Br, 32.40; Co, 12.05%. Found: S, 6.48; N, 8.55; Br, 32.53; Co, 11.87%.

Bis(N-Benzoyl-N'-o-aminophenyl thiocarbamide) tetranitrato dicobalt(II), $[\text{Co}_2(\text{BAPTC})_2(\text{NO}_3)_4]$: This was obtained as tata red crystals in a manner analogous to the tetra bromo complexes. Analysis: Calculated for $\text{Co}_2(\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{13}\text{N}_3\text{OS})_2\text{Br}_4$: S, 6.49; N, 8.53; Br, 32.09; Cu, 12.89%. Found: S, 6.52; N, 8.61; Br, 31.83; Cu, 12.85%.

Bis(N-Benzoyl-N'-o-aminophenyl thiocarbamide) tetrachloro dinickel(II), $[\text{Ni}_2(\text{BAPTC})_2\text{Cl}_4]$: Ethanolic solution of the ligand and nickel(II) chloride were mixed in the molar ratio 1 : 1 with constant stirring under reflux $\sim 70^\circ$ for about 2 hrs. It was then allowed to cool during which a silver grey precipitate was obtained which was analysed after being dried *in vacuo*. Analysis: Calculated for $\text{Ni}_2(\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{13}\text{N}_3\text{OS})_2\text{Cl}_4$: S, 7.98; N, 10.48; Cl, 17.72; Ni, 14.65%. Found: S, 7.93; N, 10.52; Cl, 17.60; Ni, 14.56%.

Bis(N-Benzoyl-N'-o-aminophenyl thiocarbamide) tetranitrato dinickel(II), $[\text{Ni}_2(\text{BAPTC})_2(\text{NO}_3)_4]$: This was prepared as chassis red crystals by adopting the above procedure. Analysis: Calculated for $\text{Ni}_2(\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{13}\text{N}_3\text{OS})_2(\text{NO}_3)_4$: S, 7.05; N, 15.43; Ni, 12.98%. Found: S, 7.12; N, 15.30; Ni, 12.78%.

Attempts to prepare the perchlorato complexes of Co(II) and Ni(II) and bromo complex of Ni(II) were unsuccessful.

The complexes are highly insoluble in water but slightly soluble in common organic solvents like dioxan, methyl cyanide, dimethylformamide, methanol and benzene.

Analyses and physical measurements: The constituent parts of each compound have been analysed by established analytical methods²³ such as copper by iodometry, nickel as dimethylglyoximate nickel(II), cobalt as its oxinate, sulphur as barium sulphate, halogens as their respective silver halides and nitrogen by semimicro combustion method.

The magnetic moments were measured at room temperature by Gouy method. Mercury(II) tetrathiocyanato cobaltate(II) $\text{Hg}[\text{Co}(\text{CNS})_4]$ was used as the standard²⁴. A Beckman IR-12 spectrophotometer was used to record the infrared spectra in KBr pellets. Electronic spectra of the ligand and its complexes were obtained employing Carry

17 D spectrophotometer in A.R. methanol. Weighing of the samples was done in Metler H 20 balance with microprocessor for spectral measurements.

Results and Discussion

The ligand can exist in different tautomeric forms (Fig. 1 a, b, c, d and e). However, the important features of the ir spectra discussed below provide evidence in favour of the structural form (a).

Fig. 1

In the region $3320-3000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ the ir spectra of the ligand show a broad band which represents a series of overlapping stretching vibrations corresponding to NH_2 and NH groups. The width further manifests that the NH_2 group is involved in intramolecular hydrogen bonding. The CH stretching vibrations of aromatic ring which usually lies in the region $3100-3000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ seems to have been enveloped by the NH and NH_2 stretching vibrations.

In all the metal complexes other than copper three or four bands with reduced intensity appear, which are located at ~ 3320 (s), 3260 (m), 3120 (w) and 3040 (m) cm^{-1} . Coordination of metal through nitrogen should cause splitting of these bands and decrease in their intensities⁶. In our opinion both the bands in the middle arise due to the splitting of NH_2 stretching vibration of the ligand keeping the vibrational energy of the NH group unaffected. The NH_2 stretching vibrations of aromatic amine appears below 3250 cm^{-1} and NH groups $\sim 3330\text{ cm}^{-1}$ similar to the amide respectively. The 3040 cm^{-1} band corresponds to the CH stretching vibrations of phenyl groups. The spectra of copper complexes show a broad asymmetric band in the region $3580-3000\text{ cm}^{-1}$. The nature of this band suggests the splitting of NH_2 group in this region which in turn participates in coordination to the metal ion.

Further evidence in support of structure (a) is indicated by the absence of any S-H band for the ligand in the region $2600-2400\text{ cm}^{-1}$. On the other hand, a medium band is observed at $\sim 1215\text{ cm}^{-1}$

which is susceptible to coordination with the metal ions and may be attributed to C=S stretching vibration⁶.

In the region 1700-1340 cm^{-1} the ligand as well as the metal complexes show four to five bands. Some of these bands are due to phenyl ring vibrations. The first strong band appears at $\sim 1670 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. Considering its intensity and sharpness this band is assigned to C=O stretching vibration⁷. It undergoes a shift to a lower frequency region in all the metal complexes and appears near 1600 cm^{-1} .

A strong band is observed at $\sim 1520 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ which seems to arise due to $\nu_{\text{C-N}}$ vibration^{8,9} of the ligand. The band is broad, perhaps due to the mixing of phenyl ring vibrations. It undergoes a blue shift in the metal complexes and appears at $\sim 1550 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ indicating an increased double bond character of ν_{as} as NCN vibration.

Three vibrational bands in the region 1640-1300 cm^{-1} are located at 1640, 1595 and 1340 cm^{-1} which are medium to strong in intensity. The first two bands arise due to the deformation vibration of NH_2 group and C=C vibrations of phenyl ring while the latter may be due to the combination bands of N-C-N and C=S stretching vibration.

The next band appearing in the ligand at 1215 cm^{-1} and assigned to C=S stretching vibration is susceptible to coordination. In all the metal complexes it shifts to a lower frequency region⁷ as expected and appears at $\sim 1165 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, clearly manifesting coordination of the sulphur atom with the metal ions.

Three bands observed in the ligand are precisely located at 1270, 1240 and 1150 cm^{-1} . Some of these bands are also observed in the metal complexes undergoing minor vibrations in their positions. These bands may be attributed to the 1 : 2 disubstituted phenyl ring¹⁰.

Two other bands are noticed in the spectra of the ligand at ~ 750 and 720 cm^{-1} . These bands shift in an irregular way in the metal complexes and probably arise due to out-of-plane CH bending absorptions of the disubstituted aromatic ring¹⁰.

Additional bands appear in the nitrate complexes at ~ 1500 , 1300, 1020 and 930 cm^{-1} which can be attributed to $\nu_{\text{N-O}}$ of the coordinated NO_3^- group¹¹. Perchlorate complexes show three significant bands at ~ 1260 (w), 1130 (s) and 1000 (w) cm^{-1} which can be assigned to ν_{as} , ν_{s} and ν_1 vibrations respectively¹².

The above ir spectral data logically lead us to suggest that the ligand is coordinated to the metal ion through amino nitrogen, sulphur and oxygen atoms. All the complexes are found to possess low magnetic moments. The low values may be due to spin-spin interaction (discussed later). Considering the ir spectra and magnetic moment values a binuclear structure (Fig. 2) is proposed for the complexes.

Fig. 2

Electronic spectra and magnetic properties : The uv spectrum of the ligand contains three absorption bands near 31,250, 41,640, 49,500 cm^{-1} . The molar extinction coefficients are found to be 24,340, 41,640 and 49,500 respectively. Considering the intensity, width and ϵ values it may be concluded that these bands may arise due to either $n \rightarrow \sigma^*$ or $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition¹³.

Copper(II) complexes of stoichiometry $[\text{Cu}_2(\text{BAPTC})_2\text{X}_4]$ possess magnetic moments in the range 1.08-1.20 B.M. The low value may be due to either partial reduction of copper(II) to copper(I) state during the synthesis of the complexes or quenching of paramagnetism due to spin-spin interaction. The oxidation state^{14,15} of copper in the complexes was tested and found to be present in +2 state. Besides, copper(II) concentration in the complexes was estimated volumetrically by decomposing them in an atmosphere of nitrogen. It was found that copper is present quantitatively as copper(II) ion in these complexes. This leads us to suggest that the low magnetic moment arises due to spin-spin interaction of the copper(II) ions, resulting partial quenching of paramagnetism.

The electronic spectra of these complexes show one or two broad band(s) in the region 14,000-18,800 cm^{-1} and a charge transfer band near 25,500 cm^{-1} . Copper(II) carboxylates which are diamagnetic show three bands at 11,000, 13,500 and 26,000 cm^{-1} ¹⁶. Another diamagnetic copper(II) complex with diazoaminobenzene¹⁷ shows two bands at 14,900 and 18,800 cm^{-1} which are assigned to $d_{xy} \rightarrow d_{z^2}$ and $d_{xy} \rightarrow d_{x^2-y^2}$ respectively. Tsuchida and coworkers^{18,19} indicated that all the copper complexes in which the paramagnetism is partially or completely quenched, absorb around 26,600 cm^{-1} . Khullar *et al.*²⁰ also reported another diamagnetic copper(II) complex with 2-mercapto benzothiazole to have absorbed at $\sim 24,400 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. However, spectra of our complexes show both ligand field and charge transfer bands like the spectra of copper(II) complexes with diazoaminobenzene.

The visible absorption spectra of nickel(II) complexes show broad asymmetric bands near about 10,200, 12,000, 15,500 and 18,500 cm^{-1} followed by a strong band at 27,000 cm^{-1} . In an octahedral approximation, the first two bands can be assigned to the split components of ${}^3\text{A}_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3\text{T}_{2g}$, (ν_1) i.e., ${}^3\text{B}_{1g} \rightarrow {}^3\text{B}_{2g}$ and ${}^3\text{B}_{1g} \rightarrow {}^3\text{E}_g$ and the next two to that of ${}^3\text{A}_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3\text{T}_{1g}$ (F), (ν_2) i.e., ${}^3\text{B}_{1g} \rightarrow {}^3\text{E}_g$ and ${}^3\text{B}_{1g} \rightarrow {}^3\text{A}_{2g}$ transitions respectively in tetragonal ligand field. The high frequency band corresponds to ${}^3\text{A}_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3\text{T}_{1g}$ (P), (ν_3) transition. The complexes exhibit low magnetic moments (2.1-2.34 B.M.) at

room temperature which may be attributed to partial quenching of paramagnetism because of spin-spin interaction.

The cobalt(II) complexes show a band system in the region 16,000-20,000 cm^{-1} which possesses the characteristic features of the electronic spectra of known octahedral complexes. The spectral transitions can be unambiguously interpreted to arise due to ligand field transition of the octahedral component of the cobalt(II) complex and may be assigned to ${}^4T_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$ transition in an approximately octahedral field. Besides, the charge transfer band appears at about 27,000 cm^{-1} . The magnetic moment values lie in the range of 2.85-2.93 B.M. The lower moments in these complexes may arise either due to electron pairing in the formation of strong covalent bond involving the use of 3d electron of cobalt(II) ion or spin-spin interaction.

Fungicidal activity: The antifungal activity of the ligand and its metal complexes was assayed by the method of Horsfall²¹ using the agar plate techniques. Three different organisms viz. *Aspergillus niger*, *Fusarium oxysporium* and *Helminthosporium oryzae* were used. The evaluation was carried out at 1000 ppm in dioxan and the number of replications in each case was three. The percentage of inhibition was calculated as follows:

$$\text{Percentage of inhibition} = \frac{X - Y}{X} 100$$

where X = area of colony in control plate; Y = area of colony in test plate

The fungicidal activity displayed by various compounds is summarised in Table 1.

TABLE 1—FUNGICIDAL SCREENING: AVERAGE PERCENTAGE INHIBITION AFTER 5 DAYS OF COLONY GROWTH AT 1000 ppm

Sl. No.	Compounds	Temp. = $31 \pm 1^\circ$		
		<i>A. niger</i>	<i>F. oxysporium</i>	<i>H. oryzae</i>
1.	BAPTC	49.0	53.8	32.2
2.	$[\text{Cu}_2(\text{BAPTC})_2\text{Cl}_4]$	94.5	76.2	54.2
3.	$[\text{Cu}_2(\text{BAPTC})_2\text{Br}_4]$	54.7	54.1	65.4
4.	$[\text{Cu}_2(\text{BAPTC})_2(\text{NO}_2)_4]$	57.4	55.0	65.3
5.	$[\text{Cu}_2(\text{BAPTC})_2(\text{ClO}_4)_4]$	50.3	62.9	56.6
6.	$[\text{Ni}_2(\text{BAPTC})_2\text{Cl}_4]$	56.4	57.0	51.9
7.	$[\text{Ni}_2(\text{BAPTC})_2(\text{NO}_2)_4]$	89.8	58.0	65.4
8.	$[\text{Co}_2(\text{BAPTC})_2\text{Cl}_4]$	88.2	58.3	91.3
9.	$[\text{Co}_2(\text{BAPTC})_2\text{Br}_4]$	72.3	56.2	73.2
10.	$[\text{Co}_2(\text{BAPTC})_2(\text{NO}_2)_4]$	27.4	42.9	24.8

The fungicidal data reveal that all the complexes except compound no. 10 are physiologically more active than the ligand. The reason may perhaps be due to the presence of C=O and C=S groups in

the ligand as well as its complexes. This observation is more or less in accordance with the observation of Horsfall and coworkers². Hence compound nos. 2-9 may serve as antifungal agents against the said organisms.

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